

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF DIGITAL VERNIER CALIPER IN THE EVALUATION OF TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT MOBILITY IN PATIENTS WITH TEMPOROMANDIBULAR DISORDER: A PRELIMINARY REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Measurements of the range of motions of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) using a caliper are crucial in treating and assessing temporomandibular disorders alongside oral and dental health. This study aims to investigate the validity and reliability of a digital vernier caliper in assessing TMJ mobility in patients with temporomandibular disorder. Twelve female patients aged between 21 and 62 with temporomandibular disorder participated in the study. Active range of motions of depression (maximum mouth opening), right laterotrusion, left laterotrusion, and protrusion were assessed. Overjet and overbite measurements were also investigated. A universal ruler was used for the convergent validity of the caliper. Reliability was assessed through intra-rater reliability, inter-rater reliability, and test-retest reliability. The digital caliper has convergence with the universal ruler in depression ($r = .606$, $p = .037$), right laterotrusion ($r = .758$, $p = .004$), left laterotrusion ($r = .936$, $p < .001$), protrusion ($r = .758$, $p = .004$), overjet ($r = .922$, $p < .001$) and overbite ($r = .905$, $p < .001$). It has an intra-rater reliability in depression (ICC = .771), right laterotrusion (ICC = .904), left laterotrusion (ICC = .947), protrusion (ICC = .924), overjet (ICC = .945) and overbite (ICC = .950) in a session. In addition, it has inter-rater reliability in depression (ICC = .774), right laterotrusion (ICC = .890), left laterotrusion (ICC = .831), protrusion (ICC = .913), overjet (ICC = .994) and overbite (ICC = .975) in a session. Moreover, it has test-retest reliability in depression (ICC = .799), right laterotrusion (ICC = .943), left laterotrusion (ICC = .857), protrusion (ICC = .897), overjet (ICC = .973) and overbite (ICC = .979) between two sessions with a week interval. This study has concluded that the digital vernier caliper is a valid and reliable tool for evaluating TMJ mobility and orthodontics. The current data highlight that it can be used in observational and interventional studies examining the mobility of the temporomandibular joint.

Keywords: Temporomandibular joint, digital vernier caliper, validity, reliability

INTRODUCTION

Temporomandibular disorders are a common condition among musculoskeletal patients. In addition to the ruler, the vernier caliper is widely used in physiotherapy and oral health for evaluation and treatment. Evaluation in clinical trials needs to be valid and reliable. Therefore, whether universal rulers or mechanical calipers are to be used, their validity and reliability must have been previously proven in humans.

Studies show that the ruler (Walker et al., 2000) and mechanical caliper (Best et al., 2013) are valid and reliable. However, no evidence in the literature suggests that the digital vernier caliper is valid and reliable for evaluating temporomandibular joints in patients with temporomandibular disorders or other medical conditions.

This study aimed to investigate the validity and reliability of digital vernier calipers for measuring the temporomandibular joint range of motion in patients with temporomandibular disorder.

The alternative hypotheses included in this study are as follows:

1. Using a digital vernier caliper to measure temporomandibular joint ranges of motion in patients with temporomandibular disorder is a valid procedure.
2. Using a digital vernier caliper to measure temporomandibular joint ranges of motion in patients with temporomandibular disorder has intra-rater reliability.
3. Using a digital vernier caliper to measure temporomandibular joint ranges of motion in patients with temporomandibular disorder has inter-rater reliability.
4. Using a digital vernier caliper to measure temporomandibular joint ranges of motion in patients with temporomandibular disorder has inter-session (test-retest) reliability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a validity-reliability study. Convergent validity between a universal ruler and a digital vernier caliper was examined. Inter-rater, intra-rater, and inter-session (test-retest) reliability were also examined. To examine test-retest reliability, the test was repeated after one week. To examine inter-rater reliability, the second rater was administered the test again 5 minutes after the first rater completed the test.

This study was conducted at the Training and Research Center for Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation of Karabük University. Twelve patients with temporomandibular joint complaints applied to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery of Oral & Dental Health Hospital in Karabük and were referred to the center. Patients were investigated and diagnosed by an experienced Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeon following clinical and radiological evaluation by Axis I of the Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (Schiffman et al., 2014). An informed consent form was obtained from the patients. The study followed the Declaration of Helsinki on medical protocol and ethics. Ethics committee approval was received for this study from the ethics committee for clinical research of Kastamonu University (Date: October 4, 2023, Number: 2023-KAEK-108).

Patients aged 18-65 years with temporomandibular disorder were included in the study. Patients with the following features were excluded from this study: (1) Orthodontic treatments, (2) trismus, (3) maxillary or mandibular surgery, (4) pregnancy, (5) breastfeeding, (6) maxillary or mandibular

malformations, (7) maxillary or mandibular significant traumas, and (8) any systemic disease such as neurological, psychiatric, immunological, rheumatological, oncological, etc. that may affect the temporomandibular joint physiology and evaluation.

Measurements

Depression: The patient was asked to open the mouth as far as possible in a sitting position. The surface of the upper and lower central teeth was accepted as a reference. A universal ruler or caliper measured the vertical distance between the two references.

Right laterotrusion: The patient was asked to move the mandibula to the right as far as possible in a sitting position. The line between the upper center teeth and the line between the lower center teeth was accepted as a reference. A universal ruler or caliper measured the horizontal distance between the two references.

Left laterotrusion: The patient was asked to move the mandibula to the left as far as possible in a sitting position. The line between the upper center teeth and the line between the lower center teeth was accepted as a reference. A universal ruler or caliper measured the horizontal distance between the two references.

Protrusion: The patient was asked to move the mandibula forward as far as possible in a sitting position. The surface of the upper and lower central teeth was accepted as a reference. A universal ruler or caliper measured the sagittal distance between the two references.

Overjet: The patient is seated with the teeth in contact, and the mouth comfortably closed. A universal ruler or caliper measured the sagittal distance between the upper and lower incisors.

Overbite: The patient sits with teeth in contact and mouth comfortably closed. The lower incisor tooth was marked with a horizontal line with a pointed, non-toxic pen. The patient was asked to open the mouth halfway. The vertical distance between the line and the upper edge of the lower incisor was then measured with a universal ruler or caliper.

Validity and reliability

Convergent validity: Variables were measured three times for both caliper and ruler. The correlation between the means of the measurements was analyzed.

Intra-rater reliability: The agreement between a rater's three measurements for a single session was analyzed.

Inter-rater reliability: The first rater measured a movement three times and averaged the three measurements. 5 min later, the second rater measured the same movement three times and averaged these three measurements. The agreement between the averages was analyzed.

Inter-session (test-retest) reliability: The first rater measured a movement three times and averaged the three measurements in the first session. One week later, the same rater measured and averaged the same movement three times. The agreement between averages was analyzed.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed in Jamovi version 2.3.21. The statistical significance level was accepted as $p < .05$. The assumption of normal distribution was evaluated by the Shapiro-Wilk test. Descriptive statistics for numerical variables are shown as median (minimum; maximum) and mean

± standard deviation values. For categorical variables, frequency (n) and percentage values are given. Convergent validity was analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient. Reliability analyses were conducted on the intraclass correlation coefficient in two-way and agreement type. The following rule of thumb was used to interpret the size of a correlation coefficient for convergent validity: $.00 \leq r < .20$ as very weak, $.20 \leq r < .40$ as weak, $.40 \leq r < .60$ as moderate, $.60 \leq r < .80$ as strong relationship, and $.80 \leq r < 1.00$ as very strong (Evans, 1996). The following rule of thumb was used to interpret the size of an intraclass correlation coefficient: $ICC < .5$ as poor, $.5 \leq ICC < .75$ as moderate, $.75 \leq ICC < .9$ as good, and $.90 \leq ICC$ as excellent (Koo & Li, 2016).

RESULTS

The digital caliper has convergence with the universal ruler in depression ($r = .606$, $p = .037$), right laterotrusion ($r = .758$, $p = .004$), left laterotrusion ($r = .936$, $p = <.001$), protrusion ($r = .758$, $p = .004$), overjet ($r = .922$, $p = <.001$) and overbite ($r = .905$, $p = <.001$). (Table 1).

Table 1. Validity analysis

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Convergent validity</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Depression	$r = .606$.037
Right laterotrusion	$r = .758$.004
Left laterotrusion	$r = .936$	<.001
Protrusion	$r = .758$.004
Overjet	$r = .922$	<.001
Overbite	$r = .905$	<.001

It has an intra-rater reliability in depression ($ICC = .771$), right laterotrusion ($ICC = .904$), left laterotrusion ($ICC = .947$), protrusion ($ICC = .924$), overjet ($ICC = .945$) and overbite ($ICC = .950$) in a session. In addition, it has inter-rater reliability in depression ($ICC = .774$), right laterotrusion ($ICC = .890$), left laterotrusion ($ICC = .831$), protrusion ($ICC = .913$), overjet ($ICC = .994$) and overbite ($ICC = .975$) in a session. Moreover, it has test-retest reliability in depression ($ICC = .799$), right laterotrusion ($ICC = .943$), left laterotrusion ($ICC = .857$), protrusion ($ICC = .897$), overjet ($ICC = .973$) and overbite ($ICC = .979$) between two sessions with a week interval. (Table 2).

Table 2. Reliability analysis

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Intra-rater reliability</i>	<i>Inter-rater reliability</i>	<i>Test-retest reliability</i>
Depression	$ICC = .771$	$ICC = .774$	$ICC = .799$
Right laterotrusion	$ICC = .904$	$ICC = .890$	$ICC = .943$
Left laterotrusion	$ICC = .947$	$ICC = .831$	$ICC = .857$
Protrusion	$ICC = .924$	$ICC = .913$	$ICC = .897$
Overjet	$ICC = .945$	$ICC = .994$	$ICC = .973$
Overbite	$ICC = .950$	$ICC = .975$	$ICC = .979$

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to assess the validity and reliability of a digital vernier caliper in measuring temporomandibular joint mobility in patients with temporomandibular disorder. Significant agreement was demonstrated between the digital vernier caliper and the universal ruler for all measurements. Strong convergence is found in depression, right laterotrusion, and protrusion. Left laterotrusion, overjet, and overbite also showed very strong convergence. Depression demonstrated good intra-rater, inter-rater, and test-retest reliability. Right, laterotrusion demonstrated good inter-rater reliability but excellent intra-rater and test-retest reliability. Left laterotrusion demonstrated good inter-rater and test-retest reliability but excellent intra-rater reliability. Protrusion demonstrated excellent intra-rater and inter-rater reliability but good test-retest reliability. Overjet and overbite demonstrated excellent intra-rater, inter-rater, and test-retest reliability.

There are some limitations in this study. The first limitation is that patients were not diagnosed according to temporomandibular subgroups. Secondly, the number of raters is limited to two. Thirdly, the passive range of motion was not evaluated. Fourthly, measurements were performed only in the sitting position.

CONCLUSION

This study has concluded that the digital vernier caliper is a valid and reliable tool for evaluating TMJ mobility and orthodontics. The current data highlight that it can be used in observational and interventional studies examining the mobility of the temporomandibular joint.

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